

Outfits and Infits: Accessing the Full Experience of Clothing Style for Design Research

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Abstract

This paper introduces the research of a multidisciplinary group of designers with backgrounds in illustration, animation, fashion, games, photography and media production whose commonality lies in the observation of people. They all translate human physical characteristics such as stance, posture, gait, mannerism, gesture and dress using a variety of media as important empathic sensibilities within their respective professions.

The group is pooling their experience in a project that uses kinematic analysis and digital media to capture aspects of human emotion that are expressed through personal appearance, particularly in relation to clothing style and the role that it plays in the animation of the body and in self-presentation. One of the project's aims is to develop interactive visual tools, which will help designers learn more of the interwoven sociality of people and their clothing. The authors supply an explanation of context, provide examples of the first of such visual tools and indicate potential applications.

Keywords: affect, body, clothing, design, haptics, kinesics, personal, sociality, somatics, style, tools.

Outfits: Artefactual communication and semiotics

Fashion and clothing have been widely interpreted as communicative, cultural, social phenomena and it is now understood that we each make daily decisions regarding the status and social role of the people we meet, based on what they are wearing. Many 20th century social commentators e.g. Simmel (1971), Veblen (1994) and Barthes, (1983) interpreted fashion as a symbolic activity relating to the outward display of social and taste distinctions. These influential modernist observers saw fashion as a symbolic code; a constant cycle of change where styles are taken up and abandoned as soon as they no longer clearly express the social identity of the wearer.

The post-modern interpretation of objects including clothing, has been concerned with their ambiguity. For instance, when Barnard (1996, 160:161), draws together the work of several writers in consideration of the 'undecidability' of the meaning of stiletto heeled shoes, he explains that 'the stiletto is constituted intertextually, in that it is the object of medical, moral, fashionable and industrial or technological discourses '. Thus the meaning of an object is produced in terms of its relations to other objects and in terms of its place in various texts or

discourses. Barnard's stiletto exemplar is a persuasive development on the modernist's view where meanings are fixed in terms of primarily gender or class, but it is remarkable that in no part of his account are the corporeal feelings or the personal emotions of actually *wearing* stilettos discussed. For instance, what of the somatic experience stimulated by the redistribution of the stiletto's wearer's weight? Or the attention to self produced by the personal timpani of such heels on wood, tarmac, cobblestone or escalator? He refers to the change of posture created by stilettos, where the bosom is thrust higher and the stomach pulled in to create a different female body shape, but this is acknowledged from the viewpoint of an observer. There is a sense in Barnard's description that the shoes are being discussed from a distance, as though they exist in a book to be 'read' or only to be seen.

'A Second Skin' brings together a collection of writing about personal experiences of clothes and perhaps this account by Levy can be interpreted as an attempt to portray the tacit, emotional communication of footwear:

'When I was seventeen and bought my first pair of brothel creepers from Shelleys' I knew they would never be worn with socks. It has always been clear to me that men and women who wear shoes without socks are destined to become my friends and lovers. These sockless people have a kind of abandon and suppleness in their body. They walk with zip. At the same time they manage to look both nonchalant and excitable. To not wear socks is to be alert but not hearty. To not wear socks is not to pretend that love is forever'. (Levy, 1998:8-10)

Unlike Barnard's externalised meanings of the stiletto, Levy's account of the affect of footwear refers to *embodied* perception, where physical sensations and emotions are communicated.

Lurie has proposed clothing as a formal language with a socially determined grammar and vocabulary (Lurie, 1992). Her interesting book is full of human images and readings of what clothing 'says' to the onlooker about the wearer, but there is little attempt to consider inner feelings, these are just presumed to concur with the external signifiers. For instance, when referring to styles that are made up of an inner and outer layer as a possible metaphor for inner and outer self, she seems at first to be hinting at a more intimate level of engagement. But she writes: 'The wearing of a white shirt with a dark suit does not mean that you are

outwardly serious and inwardly honest and trustworthy, merely that this character type has always been considered desirable in business and the professions' (Lurie, 1992: 246). Reference to the moral values symbolised by the businessman's *outfit* may imply an emotional connection between a wearer's senses and signifying appearance, but this is not referenced in her account. She does not mention for instance, the haptic experience of entering or containment with in a white shirt, like feeling fresh or clean or a sense of personal renewal, or indeed the associated psychological tensions related to keeping it clean and white.

It has been argued by some artists and designers that an essentially hermeneutic view, i.e. one that considers our reality as a text that we are constantly in the process of interpreting, has enforced a sense that 'the meanings evoked by a designed object are located predominantly outside of the self. We tend to believe that designed objects are meaningful only by way of reference beyond themselves, towards other things' (Aldrich, 2004: 367-371). This arouses a fear that 'the world of objects risks becoming separated from the world of people' (Aldrich, 2004: 368) and that ultimately an understanding of what makes up our existence as a lived reality may become impoverished. By interpreting dress only as overt graphic communication, as **outfits** that perform a kind of social semaphore, we deny its affecting intimacy and perpetuate a certain way of thinking about the meanings of clothes that is strongly related to semiotics. The various interpretations of dress as a symbolic code, as intertextual, or as a language have coherence, but as exegesis cannot fully express clothing's tacit, sensual affect.

It is possible then, that the governance of semiotics has encouraged a particular interpretation of clothing that has been called 'Fashion' and a *reading* of clothing and apparel where **outfits** have been deemed more noteworthy than '**infits**'. The personalising, inner experience of wearing clothing style and the affecting qualities that supplement (or perhaps mobilise) outward semiotic expressions, have been largely ignored. Therefore the ontological implications of such feelings for the wearer have not been seriously considered.

Infits: a sensual realm of ideals

Researchers have begun to find ways to consider clothing and personal emotion. Of particular relevance is the recent work of anthropologists Banerjee and Miller (2003) who gained empathy for the lives of women in India today through their innovative investigation "The

Sari'. This focused on the sari not just as an object of clothing, five metres of decorated cotton cloth, but as a 'lived garment'. In an evocative introduction, the authors ask us to imagine that we have encountered a sari as it envelops the body of a young woman:

'Suddenly the cloth becomes alive: it exaggerates her vivacity as she turns around, her elegance as the pleats rustle at her ankles, her flirtatiousness as it slowly threatens to slide off her shoulder, her authority and dexterity as she controls its folds. Meanwhile, though we may not realise it, the sari is also scratching her with its home made rice starch, and scaring her with its constant threats to lose its shape.'

Their work combines photographic record, individual narratives and anthropological analysis and allows us not only to assimilate the personal aesthetic of several very different Indian women, but also their 'thought and felt encounter with the world' (Banerjee and Miller, 2003). The authors advise that: 'a study of clothing should not be cold: it has to be involved in the tactile, sensual, emotional, intimate world of feelings'. Their ethnography conveys the embodied meanings of the sari and how it feels to be a woman in modern India. The authors demonstrate that wearers of the sari share a collective, physical and emotional experience but also that this arouses individual reactions and feelings. Empathy forms a basis from which questions may be asked about why particular people feel about clothing as they do, or how populations relate to issues of sociality, individuality or modernity. They conclude: 'In the hybrid world of everyday life, it is often these intimate and sensual realms that are the most effective in determining the acceptability of regimes of thought that we call reason and rationality. Through the realm of clothing, we can see how for most peoples, systems of thinking about the world also have to "feel" right' (Banerjee and Miller, 2003).

The affect of clothing varies from culture to culture, but there is no reason to suppose that it is lesser or in any way less revealing to the researcher. Sweetman writes of fashion and adornment in the West as practices that impact not only on our appearance but also on our personal experience of the body and how it can be used. By referring to his own contrasting experiences of wearing a tailored suit or of jogging pants and a tee shirt, he points out how differing materials and styles of garments demand different 'gait, posture and demeanor'. (Sweetman, 2001). In spite of increasing eclecticism within fashion, our style choices are even now partially structured by age, gender, occupation, sexuality, ethnicity and class. Sweetman observes that: 'Soldiers or cabin-attendants, schoolchildren or clubbers, fashion

victims or accountants: such groups are linked not only through their shared adoption of particular signifiers but also through their shared experience of the feel of the garments in question and the restrictions and possibilities that their materiality entails' (Sweetman, 2001).

So the sari, a pair of jeans, the tailored suit, or the uniform of the cabin attendant, can be interpreted as outward signals of ethnicity, gender, occupation or social role, but also as embodiments of the lived realities of their wearers: of differing ways of being.

Lived garments: The study of the clothed body in motion

There is a likelihood of strong emotional connections between the objective materiality of clothing and inner, subjective experience. How can we more closely observe the role that clothing plays in an individual's sense of their own body, their own self? For instance, how does it affect everyday posture, stance, mannerism and movement?

Among the earliest studies of human and animal movement are those of Edward Muybridge who in the mid to late 1800's made extensive studies on the basis of sequential still photographs. He documented the human figure in action as a means to present the body for further study by artists, scientists and physicians. The naked figures were not intended to express the particular personal characteristics of individuals, they were presented as generic anatomical analysis. The movement sequences are very much influenced by the classical traditions within art at that time e.g. 'woman turning and holding water jug for kneeling companion' or 'woman turning while carrying fan and flowers' and seem rather ridiculous as portrayals of everyday activity. Nakedness makes the models appear bizarrely characterless to eyes that are used to interpreting human identity through contemporary clothing.

But as well as horses, dogs and naked humans, Muybridge filmed people with their clothes *on* and this work in particular establishes the potential of the video sequence for the study of the contemporary clothed body. These visual records can now be re-interpreted as demonstrations of the *affect* of clothing e.g. the way that a gown influenced dance movement (Figure 1), or that a straw hat was tipped in social greeting (Figure 2).

Figure 1, 'Woman Pirouetting' (Muybridge, 1984)

The sequences convey how people expressed their contemporaneity 120 years ago through dress and personal appearance and serve to remind us that the social meanings of gesture and posture are constantly changing.

Figure 2, Man and straw hat.

Muybridge's frame by frame record reveals not only human locomotion but also the role of clothing in the styling and animation of the body, the sequences indicate the potential of kinematic analysis for the study of the *contemporary* clothed body.

Could a movie sequence such as 'woman wearing hipster jeans and cropped tee shirt, using mobile phone' hint at a way forward for the research context outlined in this paper?

Blue jeans and demeanour

Much of our contemporary clothing in the West is termed 'casual' in relation to the more formal, stricter style regimes of the past. The relaxing of dress codes is seen to reflect a progressive lessening of rigid class or gender structuring within society. For instance, denim and jeans currently supply everyday clothing for large sectors of society; in 2003 jeans sales in the UK topped 62 million pairs (Mintel). In this case, casual refers to a style of clothing but also to the appearance and manner of its wearer. As a version of trousers: 'orig., a loose-fitting garment of cloth worn by men, covering the loins and legs to the ankles; sometimes said to have been worn over close-fitting breeches or pantaloons; now applied generally to any two-legged outer garment worn by both sexes, and extending from the waist usually to the ankles' (OED), jeans are strongly implicated in stance and locomotion, as they clothe the supporting, propelling limbs that connect to our feet and join us to the earth.

The authors were interested to learn more about 'feeling casual' and what this could tell us about 'feeling contemporary'. So we undertook a series of trial interviews, which asked ten people directly about the appeal of the denim garments they were wearing. During these interviews all respondents described their sense of wearing denim and jeans as 'comfortable' or that they made them 'feel more relaxed'. The majority also felt that denim clothing afforded a comfortable sense of 'fitting in' socially, and were able to describe their personal strategies for doing so. In some interviews, we used two video cameras to record the way their clothing was used in self presentation (Candy 2003: 28-33). We later edited the video sequences in order to isolate the figure from its surroundings, and to focus on their gestures and body movements.

In some sequences the subject's head was cropped out, in order to allow body action the centre of attention. We were thus able to capture movement, to concentrate on gestures and make comparisons between the subjects (Figure 3).

Figure 3, two examples of editing formats: individual and comparative.

The resulting movies supplemented the spoken narratives with the physical presence, attitude and gestures of the interviewee. An impression of the somatic sensations of the wearer and of clothing's role in the animation of the body, was relayed through the moving footage. Using video enabled us to speed up or slow down sequences to enable analysis of the range of movement or the shifting of body weight for instance. By grabbing stills we could see aspects of self-presentation more clearly, like the haptic components of gesture (Figure 4) for example. People touched, stroked, slapped, fingered, rubbed their clothing during the course of the interview, rested hands on hips, in belt loops, or sunk them into pockets, pivoted the hips and launched gestures from these positions of rest.

Figure 4, haptic gestures in stills grabbed from movie sequences.

Although used in a different context, this moving image method is reminiscent of the Profile of Non Verbal Sensitivity test developed in the 1970's (Rosenthal et al, 1979), which used visual and audio techniques in a test for the ability to understand non-verbal cues transmitted by facial expressions, body movements and tones of voice. In the PONS test a female researcher portrayed different scenes that involved various emotions, strong and mild, positive and negative. Scenes were videotaped on three cameras and later shown to test audiences in three visual channels – face, body and figure (figure 5). A total of eleven permutations were created by mixing visual channels with alternating audio channels, where the voice of the portrayer was filtered in different ways. The researchers were able to show empirical evidence of the similarities and differences in people's sensitivity to non-verbal communication

Surprisingly perhaps, in the account of their method the PONS researchers make no mention whatsoever of the clothing of the young woman selected to be the portrayer. Photographs show her wearing a relatively plain, simple dress of the period. It is unclear if this was chosen as particularly suitable for the needs of the project.

Figure 5, from the PONS Test (Rosenthal et al, 1979)

Like the PONS we showed finished sequences to others to seek interpretations of body language displayed, but we decided to show ours without sound in order to concentrate on non-language communication.

We are experimenting with another visual called *The Body Dictionary* (Candy, 2003). This is made up of a set of diagrams (approximately 40 to date) produced from photographs taken ‘on the street’ by the researchers. These exemplify some of the body shapes that people create through their style of dressing (figure 6). The diagrams were created by tracing over photographs, and by picking out structural seam lines to explain the shape and detail of

garments. The logic for the drawing technique comes from the conventions of fashion illustration, where garment detail and construction are conveyed via an understanding of the body. The collection of figures aims to replicate a sense of everyday social encounter and to supply an opportunity to access the almost subliminal assessments we make in response to people seen on the street or met in other public places that evidence a society. Each diagram illustrates a clothing style, while allowing its wearer to be anonymous yet to remain familiar. In this way the drawing creates characters, whose identity is made apparent only via interpretations of their clothed body. The diagrammatic style invites assessment of identity and we found that respondents were able to generate distinct personas for the characters they ‘met’ in the diagrams.

Figure 6, examples from the Body Dictionary.

They could offer their own forms of social classification; suggest which brand of clothing the figure might be wearing, make further product connections or respond to questions regarding a range of other social scenarios. As well as cultural or socio-economic forms of categorisation, descriptions of the figures also involved emotional assessments e.g that a character was shy, or lazy or arrogant, or nice-looking for instance even though faces were obscured. We think

that these judgements derive from interpretation of a synthesis of clothing and body attitude of the character and also via association with 'real' individuals.

The photographers did not pose the original subjects, attitudes taken up were individual responses to the camera, and as such show interesting aspects of self-presentation. But although body stance is in evidence, further interpretation of the affect of the clothing on the wearer is limited by lack of any expressive movement.

Sets of figures are currently being piloted by designers and marketers as aids to consider the identity and lifestyle of their consumers.

Proposals for future work

In trials, both moving and still image research methods created visual outcomes that prompted viewers to generate complex descriptions of the possible identity of the anonymised figures in the images. We consider that the techniques have potential for further development, as methods of social documentation but also as interactive tools. They 'permit' people to talk about other people and use everyday dress and personal appearance to access aspects of sociality.

Responses are by no means universal however, because when undertaking such assessments people reveal their own views and aspects of their own social circumstances. Propriety means that people are often reticent to talk about their own personal style, and because their experience is largely intuitive it is hard for them to relay it, but in many cases they have a lot to say about the style and appearance of others. We realised that when making such assessments they were indirectly telling us about themselves, by drawing on their own ideals and value systems. Through consideration of clothing style we learned a lot about people and their attitudes towards others.

The team is currently engaged in the development of visual methods that combine aspects of the basic techniques developed so far in order to continue to investigate the affect of clothing on our emotions. We intend that future kinematic analysis will incorporate illustrative digital media, in order to capture and analyse the clothed figure in motion. We will use blue/green screen methods so that moving figures can be extracted and further developed using rotoscoping in Adobe Premier and After Effects. In the longer term, the ambition is to create a group of socially expressive, virtual 'personae' for use within the study of identity.

We think that such visual techniques have potential within research that aims to examine different emotional engagements with material culture. We are particularly interested in people's feelings of contemporaneity, formality, casuality, gender, or youth and age and how these are expressed and interpreted in terms of personal appearance and style aesthetic.

Conclusion

It is thought that up to 93% of human communication takes the form of non-verbal behaviour, (Wood, 1994) and this naturally draws attention to the clothed body as a focus for study. Important aspects of one's identity are conveyed through the movement and cadence of the body: even gender can be thought of as a stylisation of the body and in this context dress is both an indicator and a producer of gender. It follows then, that social identity 'expressed through dress becomes not only an answer to the question of *who* one is, but also to *how* one is'. (Barnes and Eicher, 1992).

In the 21st century style is ubiquitous: experienced in the media, at work, at leisure and on the street. Consumers have learned to navigate a sea of available identity commodities to create seemingly mobile processes of individuation and social grouping. Quantitative data is constantly analysed regarding the social makeup of such groupings and often clothing style is interpreted as symbolic representations of identity or of 'the market'. We believe that an over commitment to semiotic analysis has meant that these social categorisation systems may currently lack depth in terms of emotion and feelings, which cannot be accessed using existing quantitative methods.

We do not consider it realistic or desirable to structure formulaic market sector categorisations. Our aim is to develop interactive, flexible tools that have the potential to be used in a number of ways by researchers in different fields, as we recognise that contemporary society is made up of a gestalt of viewpoints. We hope to develop ways to help designers and other social observers to 'see through the eyes of others' and to better interpret non-language forms of communication.

We propose that interpreting clothing as affecting *lived garments* rather than as the limited semiotic of 'fashion' offers design researchers access to a range of human experiences, where personal and social issues may be explored simultaneously. Clothing offers access to a

sensual realm of ideals where designers can learn more of the lived reality of others by paying attention to the emotionally charged experiences that are derived through our minds **and** our bodies.

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